

LOCATING THE BARRIERS AND NAVIGATING THE PATHWAYS TO WOMEN EMPOWERMENT THROUGH EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

All the levels of formal education from elementary to tertiary have a vital role for national development. Technology has been given a lot of importance in education. We are moving towards the goal of gender equity in education sector but still some road blocks are hindering the progress of women. Even in the era of women empowerment, the larger section of womenfolk across the globe is neglected in all spheres. Moreover, the degree of women empowerment is diverse across India. West Bengal is a 4th largest State of India in terms of population. In West Bengal, 77.08% is the total literacy rate as per 2011 census where is 71.16% of female and 82.67% of male. Now it is quite pertinent to reexamine where West Bengal stands at present in terms of women empowerment from the lens of education. It also seeks to unpack the dominant barriers to women empowerment through education with an objective of navigating some viable pathways to their empowerment to the fullest.

Keywords: Education, Literacy, Women Empowerment, Gender Equity, National Development.

INTRODUCTION

Women constitute almost 50% of the total population in India. Education is the key to women empowerment. Education has a positive role in the overall development of any country and society. Its holistic development calls for equal contribution from both men and women. Swami Vivekananda thus stated, “There is no chance for the welfare of the world unless the condition of woman is improved. It is not possible for a bird to fly on only one wing” (Vivekananda, 1993 as cited in Singh, 2014, p. 40). When Mahatma Gandhi said at the All India Women’s Conference in 1936, “When a woman, whom we call ‘abala’ becomes ‘sabala’, all those who are helpless will become powerful” (Gandhi, 1982 as cited in Kapoor, 2016), he actually wanted to put emphasis on the necessity of women’s freedom and strength for building a humane and exploitation free society. So, it is an important responsibility of the state to provide education to girls like boys. The development and progress of any nation is never possible if women are neglected, unaware, ignorant and uneducated. Therefore, women’s education can be an effective tool for the overall welfare of any nation. In order to develop the latent potential of women to the fullest, women’s education is essential.

As per the Census Report of 2011, West Bengal is the fourth largest state in terms of population of India and it holds the 13th position in terms of literacy. Moreover, 4.45 crore constitutes female population out of total population 9.13 crore in West Bengal. It has ratio of sex 950 females for every 1000 males. There is 71.16% female and 82.67% male literacy rate out of total 77.08% in West Bengal. As per the report of employment and unemployment surveys conducted by the Labour Bureau (Ministry of Labour and Employment, 2018) in the years 2012–13, 2013–14, and 2015–16, the working population ratios of women in West Bengal aged 15 years and above are 20.6%, 17.2%, and 20.5%, respectively. But in the era of women empowerment, the rate of female literacy is highly an area of concern. Still, girls, especially from Socio-Economically Disadvantaged Groups (SEDGs), face various challenges to complete their education at all levels. Child marriage, domestic work, forced labour, school distance from home, cultural prejudices etc. create barriers to girls' education. Let's now see what the contemporary research speak about the barriers to women empowerment in West Bengal.

RESEARCH METHOD AND MATERIALS

The present study is an analytical as well as qualitative in nature. It is chiefly based on the secondary sources of data obtained from books, journals, and education reports related to this problem. Secondary data analysis method has been applied in this study. This study has sought to address the following objectives:

- 1) To reexamine where West Bengal stands at present in terms of women empowerment through the lens of education.
- 2) To unpack the dominant barriers to women empowerment through education with an objective of navigating some viable pathways to their empowerment to the fullest.

EXAMINING THE CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH EVIDENCES

Lahane (2024) carried out a study on “educational impact on women empowerment”. Result of the study revealed that empowering women through education can bring radical changes in women's employment and social infrastructure. Sarkar (2017) studied on “Recent Status of Education, Employment and Empowerment of Women in West Bengal.” Researchers showed that the home had a positive effect on women's active participation in employment-related decision-making processes. Chakraborty and Mondal (2014) examined a study on “Role of Education in Women Empowerment: A Case Study on the Social Development of the ‘Santal’ of Birbhum District, West Bengal.” The researcher showed in the study, ‘Santal’ women were not empowered or improved because of their low social literacy rate. The researcher also said that educational improvement was essential for the social development of ‘Santal’ women in rural Bengal. Kundu and Chakraborty (2012) conducted a study on “the empowerment of Muslim women in Murshidabad district of West Bengal”. Result was revealed that participation of local NGO's could change awareness of women rights and empowerment process of Muslim women community. Mukhopadhyay (2008) carried out an investigation on the “the role of education for women empowerment at Malda district and reflection on survey of women”. The researcher found that educated and economically empowered women of Malda district can take strong decisions on any issue and stand against “Dowry system”. Sarkar and Ghosh (2021)

studied on “Empowerment of Women in West Bengal: Issues and Challenges.” Researcher had mentioned that government initiatives were not sufficient for women empowerment. As a way of empowering women, researcher had showed that the mindset of common people, media, politicians, women community will create an environment where will be no differentiate between men and women. Banerjee and Pan (2023) conducted a study on “Empowerment of Rural and Urban Women in West Bengal: A Case Study in Birbhum District”. The study showed the involvement of women at all levels through the civilization of family formation, cultural initiation, rise of economic elements. It was also revealed that empowerment of urban women was better than rural women. Khatun (2024) in a study title “Scenario of Women Empowerment: A Regional Analysis of Selected Indicators in West Bengal” showed that urban women had a higher literacy rate than rural women. It was also revealed that higher level of decision-making power among Hindu women was higher than among Muslim women. Roy and Banerjee (2024) in a study titled “Women’s Education in West Bengal: Initiatives and Challenges” showed that government initiatives to promote women’s education were effective. The whole gamut of contemporary research literature thus shows diverse factors behind the failure in achieving women empowerment in West Bengal. The present has thus intended to unpack the dominant barriers of women empowerment through education. It also aims to navigate some viable pathways of their empowerment in the present scenery.

REVIEWING THE SCENARIO OF WOMEN EDUCATION IN WEST BENGAL

West Bengal has repeatedly shown the way of women’s empowerment. ‘Satidaha’ abolition due to untiring efforts of Raja Rammohun Roy, Hindu Widow Remarriage Act by Pandit Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, establishment of Calcutta Female School as early as in 1849 by John Elliot Drinkwater Bethune were the landmark steps towards women empowerment in 19th century” (Sarkar and Ghosh, 2021). The contribution of these great thinkers to the education and empowerment of women in West Bengal and India is unforgettable. Education is the only imperative for women empowerment. In this context, the overall education rate of women in West Bengal since the 20th century is mentioned in Table No. 1 and Figure No. 1 below.

Table 1: Literacy Rate (%) in West Bengal

Year	Female	Male	Total
1901	1.2	17.9	9.8
1911	1.7	19.1	10.8
1921	2.5	21	12.3
1931	3.8	20.4	12.4
1941	8.3	29.3	19.7
1951	12.7	34.1	24.61
1961	20.3	46.6	34.46
1971	26.6	49.57	38.86

Year	Female	Male	Total
1981	34.4	56.93	48.65
1991	46.6	67.81	57.70
2001	59.68	77.02	68.64
2011	71.16	82.67	77.08

Source: Census Reports, Government of India

Figure 1: Female Literacy Rate (%) Growth in West Bengal

Source: Census Reports, Government of India

From Table 1 and Figure 1, it can be understood that since the early 20th century the female literacy rate has increased significantly along with the male literacy rate but still there is a huge gap between the male literacy rate and the female literacy rate. According to the 1901 census, the gap between male and female literacy rates was 16.7 and at the beginning of the 21st century, according to the 2001 census, the gap was 17.34. According to the 2011 census, the female literacy rate is 71.16 and the male literacy rate is 82.67, i.e. the difference between the male and female literacy rate is 11.51, which raises the question whether it is promising in the era of women empowerment in the 21st century.

Now, let's us look at the table 2 which shows the female literacy rate in terms of areas in West Bengal in comparison with whole India in the post-independence era;

Table 2: Compare Female Literacy Rate (%) Rural and Urban area of WB and India

Year	West Bengal		India	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
1951	---	---	22.33	4.87
1961	50.02	11.73	43.75	26.49
1971	54.11	18.05	52.54	26.13
1981	60.72	25.34	58.07	26.92
1991	68.25	38.12	64.05	30.17

Year	West Bengal		India	
	Urban	Rural	Urban	Rural
2001	76.14	53.82	72.86	46.13
2011	81.70	66.08	79.92	58.75

Source: Census Reports, Government of India

Table 2 represents the urban female literacy rate in West Bengal is higher than the national rate and the female literacy rate has increased gradually since independence. But the rural female literacy rate in post-independence North West Bengal was lower than the national rate till 1980. Later it increased, as seen in the female literacy rate of West Bengal (as per census 38.12% in 1991, 53.82% in 2001 and 66.08% in 2011) and the national literacy rate (as per census 30.17% in 1991, 46.13% in 2001, and 58.75% in 2011). If we review the status of school education in terms of Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in West Bengal in comparison with India, the following tables 3 and 4 reveals that the GER of girls in West Bengal is in better position at all levels of school education in terms of national rate in the last five years.

Table 3: GER by Gender and Level of School Education in India

Year	Elementary (1 to 8)			Secondary (9-10)			Higher Secondary (11-12)		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
2018-19	95.5	96.7	96.1	76.9	76.9	76.9	49.5	50.8	50.1
2019-20	97.0	98.7	97.8	78.0	77.8	77.9	50.5	52.4	51.4
2020-21	98.3	100.0	99.1	80.1	79.5	79.8	53.0	54.6	53.8
2021-22	99.3	101.1	100.1	79.7	79.4	79.6	57.0	58.2	57.6
2022-23	92.2	95.8	93.9	78.3	80.1	79.2	55.1	58.7	56.8
2023-24	90.7	92.9	91.7	76.8	78.0	77.4	54.4	58.2	56.2

Source: UDISE+, Government of India

Table 4: GER by Gender and Level of School Education in West Bengal

Year	Elementary (1 to 8)			Secondary (9-10)			Higher Secondary (11-12)		
	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total	Boys	Girls	Total
2018-19	97.8	100.8	99.3	72.4	91.1	81.5	47.2	56.6	51.7
2019-20	102.3	105.0	103.6	76.8	96.1	86.3	50.1	60.6	55.2
2020-21	108.7	110.4	109.5	82.0	100.8	91.2	53.3	64.0	58.5
2021-22	107.8	109.1	108.5	83.4	93.2	88.2	53.7	70.6	62.0
2022-23	102.8	104.2	103.5	92.5	98.6	95.5	57.3	78.0	67.5
2023-24	105.8	107.6	106.7	98.5	104.2	101.3	57.0	75.5	66.1

Source: UDISE+, Govt. of India

Tables 3 and 4 show that West Bengal’s female literacy rate at primary (1–8), secondary (9–10), and higher secondary (11–12) school levels is better than the all-India female literacy rate. Now let’s look at the gross enrollment ratio (GER) in higher education in West Bengal in comparison with India. Table 5 and figure 2 capture that GER of females in West Bengal from 2015-16 to 2021-22 is always lower than the national rate.

Table 5: Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education (18-23 years)

Year	All India			West Bengal		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
2015-16	25.4	23.5	24.5	19.1	16.2	17.7
2016-17	26.0	24.5	25.2	19.8	17.2	18.5
2017-18	26.3	25.4	25.8	19.9	17.6	18.7
2018-19	26.3	26.4	26.3	20.0	18.7	19.3
2019-20	26.9	27.3	27.1	20.3	19.6	19.9
2020-21	26.7	27.9	27.3	20.3	22.3	21.3
2021-22	28.3	28.5	28.4	25.9	26.8	26.3

Source: AISHE Reports, Ministry of Education, Govt. of India

Figure 2: Female GER (%) in All India and West Bengal

Source: AISHE Reports, Ministry of Education, Govt. of India

As a whole, girls in West Bengal are in better position than national rate in terms of literacy and GER at all levels of school education but in higher education, girls in West Bengal lag behind the national rate in terms of GER. However, the Government of West Bengal has intimated a number of schemes for accelerating the educational achievements of boys and girls in formal education. Government initiatives to make West Bengal a hub for women empowerment are noteworthy. The Education Department, Government of West Bengal has launched several schemes to ensure the education of girls and boys, especially for the education of girls. The important schemes for women empowerment through in West Bengal are listed below Table 6.

Table 6 : Educational Schemes in West Bengal

Women Empowerment Scheme	Aims / Objectives
Kanyashree Project (2013)	With this scheme, a financial benefit is provided to the women of West Bengal to sustain them in education on a regular basis. The main objective of this project of the Department of Child and Women Development, Govt. of West Bengal was to end child marriage and provide regular education for women empowerment.
Rupashree Prakalpa (2018)	It gives financial assistance to parents during the legal marriage of daughter.
Swami Vivekananda Merit-cum-Means Scholarship Scheme (revamped in the year 2016)	The initiative aims to provide higher education opportunities to a large number of meritorious and economically backward students (higher education in regular mode from Class XI) in the state.
Aikyashree Scholarship (2018-2019)	Providing financial assistance to economically weaker minority students.
Shikshashree (2014-2015)	The scheme provides scholarships for education up to Class VIII to children belonging to SC and ST communities in West Bengal whose family income is <2.5 Lac for per annum.
Sabooj Sathi (2015-2016)	The scheme encourages girls to pursue higher education by providing them with bicycles, reduces dropouts, facilitates girls' schooling and promotes girls' empowerment.
Mid-Day-Meal Programme(2003)	The Mid-Day Meal Scheme is an important one for school going students. It was started only for class I-IV But later it was upgraded to higher primary level (Class: VI-VIII). The aim of the scheme is to improve student health and school orientation.
Taruner Swapna (2022)	Financial assistance of Rs.10,000 to all students studying in class 11 and 12 in government and government aided schools in West Bengal for purchase of smart phones/tabs.

Source: Department of women & Child Development and Social Welfare, and Chief Minister's Office, Government of West Bengal, 2025.

Despite these schemes and programmes in the field of education in West Bengal, women's empowerment through education is still marginal. It is pertinent to unpack the barriers to their empowerment from the contemporary research evidences. Let's have a glance at the following hurdles in this regard.

BARRIERS TO WOMEN EMPOWERMENT FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF EDUCATION

Education is the main tool for women empowerment. However, women's empowerment is also hindered due to some reasons. The barriers to women empowerment through education in West Bengal are diverse in nature. Some of these barriers are common across India. What the research speaks are;

- 1. Illiteracy and Lack of Awareness of Parents :** Most of the parents in our society are not aware of the education of their girl child. "Negligence of parents and child marriage are the main reasons for hindering women's education" (Mukhopadhyay, 2008, p.221). We know every human being has potential, whether is a man or woman. From the time of birth, parents think of their marriage without giving priority on the desires, tastes, interests, tendencies, and abilities of the girl child. As a result, many talents of the society go into darkness prematurely.
- 2. Poverty and Early Marriage :** Many girls who enrolled in education dropped out of educational institutions due to various reasons such as poverty, early marriage, etc." Early marriage is another common feature leading parents to withdraw their girls from school, and once they are gone, very few girls return to school" (Mukhopadhyay, 2008, p.221). Child marriage is prohibited in Indian society. Marrying a girl under 18 is a punishable offense under Indian law. But many parents are giving marriage to their daughters, by ignoring this law. The people of the village believe that if girls get married early, the family gets financial relief. 58% of illiterate girls are married before the age of 18, compared to only 4% of highly educated girls. "In rural India almost 70% of girls are getting married before they are 18 and nearly 56% of married girls bear children before they are 19" (Sarkar, 2018, p.97). Moreover, rural uneducated, poor parents do not attach much importance to girls' education.
- 3. Inadequacy of Girls Schools and Teacher:** Some parents in the society who are not willing to send girls to co-educational schools. They are only interested in sending to girls' schools. Another thing is notable that many girls are also comfortable attending girls' school. The amount of girls' school is very less compared to their demand in West Bengal. Moreover, "The large number of teacher vacancies, poor quality of education and inadequate funds is a common factor in West Bengal" (Marie Lall, 2005; Sahoo 2024). According to WBCHE, there are about 681 girls' schools, 3441 Co-ed schools, and 302 boys' schools out of a total of 6771 schools at higher secondary level in West Bengal. Inadequacy of girls' schools is becoming an obstacle to women's education. Where women education is less important, there is a difficulty in finding female teachers for girls' education. Even in West Bengal lack of adequately trained female teachers is a major challenge for female education.
- 4. Lack of Hostels:** It is common to see that in the 21st century Indian education system up to higher secondary level, girls can complete their studies from home by

going to nearby educational institutions. But most rural areas do not have schools close to girls' homes. Even for the next level of education, they have to travel to educational institutions far away from home. "Distance of school from habitation in rural area of west Bengal is big problem to regular attend the school" (Sahoo, 2024). Due to lack of hostel facilities, sometimes girls have to drop out at the midway of their education.

5. **Discrimination in Curriculum:** "Girls will not be good at learning math when they enter middle school. People believe that women are good at linguistics, history, and similar art subjects that hinge on the capability of language or memory, while men are good at math, physics, and similar science subjects that require logical reasoning" (Xie & Liu, 2023). It is believed that girls are less intelligent than boys. They are not good at mathematics. Hence they are deprived of studying all these subjects along with many subjects of scholarship and technical education like computers, electronics, graphics, land surveying etc. Women's education is largely hindered due to this discrimination.
6. **Lack of school infrastructure:** Although there are some co-educational schools or girls' schools for the education of girls, there is a lack of proper infrastructure. Like-toilets, common room, proper classroom, separate drinking water system etc. "Many schools are not properly equipped with laboratory facilities, necessary teaching aids and appliances" (Sahoo, 2024). Due to lack of proper school infrastructure, many girls do not feel comfortable going to school. As a result, their education is disrupted.

THE WAY FORWARD

The difficult task is to find ways to solve ongoing problems in techno-global society. Education is the only path that can be properly used for the development of women. Education is one of the main pillars of national development. The direction of women development should be viewed through social conditions, positive aspects of education, positive view of the people etc. The following are the pathways to women empowerment through education -

- Ongoing curriculum at all levels of education needs to be diversified and reformed. According to National Curriculum Framework – 2005, "improving classroom processes and school management to implement the curricular and pedagogic shift for enhancing participation in learning process and providing success experience to all learners". A more pragmatic approach needs to be introduced at the time of framing curriculum. A diversified curriculum for girls should be developed keeping in mind the needs of home life along with general education.
- Attention must be paid to establishing equal rights for men and women in society. It is necessary to increase the employment of girls to become economically independent. For this, suitable girls' schools need to be established in rural areas. Nutritious food should be provided through mid-day meals in schools. Parents need to be made aware

of the need for women education in rural areas. Illiterate people need to be made aware of the ill effects of child marriage. West Bengal's Kanyashree Project through education should be further strengthened to stop child marriage and prevent girls from dropping out of school.

- Gender related content within the curricular needs to be addressed in a manner which promotes gender equality. Teachers must also be oriented towards overall gender sensitization in the education sector.
- Successful implementation of the Right to Education (RTE) Act, 2009 & its extension for 3-6 and 14-18 age-groups, Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) and NEP 2020 all over India. Government should encourage ICT tools and the use of internet for the study and research by women. Issues like gender-sensitization, gender mainstreaming in the educational programmes should be incorporated.
- We should make a shift in approach towards women based on sex discrimination and change our attitudes towards female education and by raising the social consciousness of the country through national media and communication effort.
- Government should also make availability of exclusive women's institutions at all levels. Gender mainstreaming perspective should be introduced in all developmental process. Equality of sexes as a major value to be inculcated through the educational process at all levels.

CONCLUSION

Considering the above discussions, it can be said that women's education is plagued with various societal barriers. The Government of West Bengal has provided many facilities for the development of women's education. In the field of education of girls, we face various problems from various aspects like political, social, economic complications etc. We have seen the lack of proper planning and implementation of girls' education. Several strategies can be devised to empower women through education. After independence, many committees and commissions have been formed for women education and empowerment in India, but women education and empowerment is still a concern in our society. But it is true that women education and empowerment will surely progress only if positive attitude is awakened among the common people of our society. Change in the attitude of the people, the awakening of values, and implementation of the Acts and laws, the main barriers to women's education and empowerment will be eradicated. Last but not the least, girls need to have confidence in themselves and be aware of all forms of violence. We hope to be able to get out of this situation and we can say it again, "The destiny of India is being shaped in her classroom". A change in people's attitude, awakening of values is expected to help overcome the root problems of women's education and

empowerment. As a result, women in West Bengal are expected to achieve more empowerment in terms of gender equality, political, social and economic etc. through education.

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